

Master in Sound and Music Computing
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Exploring Neural Audio Codec-based Contrastive Language-Audio Pre-training

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Acknowledgement

Under the Mediterranean sun, Barcelona, a city interwoven with geometry and light, shines like a dazzling pearl. As I stand on the verge of completing my two-year master's journey, I reflect on my time at the Music Technology Group (MTG), a beacon in the realm of sound and music computing. Time has flowed gently, much like the Mediterranean breeze, carrying with it shimmering waves of precious memories from these past two years of study.

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Abstract

This thesis investigates the potential of Neural Audio Codecs (NACs) to enrich the audio representation capabilities of Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining (CLAP) models. We introduce an innovative evaluation approach to systematically compare various CLAP configurations utilizing distinct audio encoder modules on the text-to-audio retrieval task. Our rigorous experimental analysis implies that NAC-based modules offer superior feature discrimination and retrieval efficacy. The research presents a methodological framework for NAC integration in CLAP models, sets new performance benchmarks, and outlines future directions, emphasizing the development of universal audio embeddings and refined pre-training techniques. Our codes are available at https://github.com/duduOliver/SMC_CodecCLAP.

Keywords: Contrastive Learning; Representation Learning; Audio Embedding Models; Neural Audio Codecs; Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining; Text-to-Audio Retrieval.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Since the advent of deep learning as the mainstay of artificial intelligence (AI), the principle that larger-scale models equate to higher performance has been a driving force behind the demand for more extensive training data. The evolution of AI research in recent years has focused on scaling up models[1, 2, 3, 4]. Since 2020, the trend has become increasingly evident with the emergence of large-scale models such as generative[5, 6] and cross-modal representation models[7, 8]. Some of these models have demonstrated remarkable generalization capabilities, allowing them to perform well across a variety of downstream tasks without fine-tuning on domain-specific data. This has led to the introduction of the concept of "Foundation models[9]," which refer to models with powerful representational abilities that can handle a wide range of downstream tasks effectively through zero-shot learning.

When it comes to model training, particularly through computational methods, the foremost consideration is how to encode our data modalities in a manner that is interpretable and comprehensible by computers, which is an essential step in computer-aided modeling. This field of study is typically classified under the umbrella of representation learning [10]. The recent emergence of Foundation models is also intrinsically linked to the significant strides made in the realm of representation learning. The year 2020 is regarded as a watershed moment for deep learning's evolution from quantitative to qualitative change, driven by breakthroughs in un-

supervised contrastive learning, which substantially advanced the field of representation learning. For example, OpenAI’s Contrastive Language-Image Pretraining (CLIP) model [8] is capable of training cross-modal models using unlabeled image data paired with natural language captions, thereby mitigating the scarcity of data that arises from the expansion of model scale and harnessing large-scale unlabeled data as a training resource. As these larger models undergo training and begin to converge, we typically anticipate an enhancement in performance, and indeed, the CLIP model has exhibited exceptional zero-shot capabilities, a level of proficiency that was not commonly seen in deep learning models from previous years. This has greatly motivated researchers to delve deeper into this area. In the wake of these developments, we have noticed researchers in the audio field, motivated by the success of the CLIP model, commencing investigations into Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining (CLAP) [11, 12, 13, 14]. They are aspiring to replicate the generalization capabilities observed in CLIP, particularly the ability to perform well in zero-shot learning scenarios.

Specifically, in the evolution of representation learning for the audio modality, we have also witnessed numerous encouraging technological advancements in recent years. The emergence of neural audio codec (NAC) [15, 16, 17] technology is a significant aspect that should not be overlooked and holds substantial potential for development. Beyond its enhanced information compression rate and high-fidelity audio vocoder capabilities, its capacity to encode audio modality into discrete tokens facilitates the harmonization of representation forms between audio and text data modalities post-representation, thereby significantly propelling the progression of audio language models[18].

However, to the best of our knowledge, there is no public research on application of neural audio codec as an audio representation method in the training of CLAP models. The CLAP model training methodology, as a strategy capable of cultivating exceptionally strong representational abilities in cross-modality pretraining models, coupled with the neural audio codec, an innovative and highly representative and restorative audio representation technique, raises the intriguing question of

whether their integration could yield a synergistic enhancement. This prospect has undoubtedly sparked our curiosity.

1.1 Motivation

Applying neural audio codecs as an audio representation method in CLAP model training represents an uncharted research frontier. Given the significant potential of both neural audio codecs and CLAP models in the domain of audio representation, this has inspired us to explore whether their combination could yield superior audio representation outcomes. We are interested in qualitatively verifying whether the representation of audio data as discrete tokens through neural audio codecs still retains a strong representational power for the audio modality.

The initiation of research in this direction will also drive the development of strategies for more effectively leveraging neural audio codec methods within the structure of CLAP models. This will lay the groundwork for future in-depth research and exploration of neural audio codec-based CLAP, potentially leading to breakthroughs in the field of audio representation and cross-modal representation learning.

1.2 Objectives

This research is propelled by a set of objectives designed to explore the uncharted territory of integrating neural audio codecs into the framework of Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining (CLAP) models. Each objective is crafted to address a specific facet of this novel approach, ensuring a comprehensive investigation.

1. **Feasibility Study:** The preliminary validation is aimed at qualitatively assessing whether audio data, once converted into discrete tokens by a neural audio codec, maintains its robust representational capabilities. Our goal is to devise experiments that evaluate the essential intrinsic features required for advanced audio analysis tasks using CLAP (Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining) models. We hypothesize that the discrete token representation can not only preserve these features but also potentially enhance them.

2. **Exploratory Experimentation:** We seek to explore and substantiate the potential of a neural audio codec-based audio encoder module as a component within the CLAP model structure. The goal is to determine if this module can be trained to develop robust audio representations, thereby establishing the viability and promise of this approach as a fruitful avenue for future research.
3. **Methodological Framework Development:** The third objective is to investigate and articulate best practices for leveraging neural audio codecs in the context of CLAP model training. This involves identifying optimal strategies for encoding, integrating, and fine-tuning the model to fully harness the representational strengths of neural audio codecs. We aim to develop a generalizable methodological framework that can serve as a guide for future research and practical implementation in the field.

Through these objectives, this thesis endeavors to contribute to the understanding of audio representation learning and to push the boundaries of audio-textual applications within AI models. The pursuit is not just to validate the current capabilities but also to lay the groundwork for innovative integrations that could transform the way audio data is processed and understood in cross-modal AI systems.

1.3 Expected Contributions

The expected contributions of this thesis are multifaceted, reflecting the depth and breadth of the research conducted on the integration of neural audio codecs within the CLAP model framework. Each contribution is designed to advance the field of audio representation learning and to foster a deeper understanding of cross-modal AI systems.

1. **Empirical Validation:** Through rigorous experimentation and analysis, we might provide empirical evidence supporting the effectiveness of neural audio codecs in bolstering the representational capabilities of CLAP models. Our results might validate the hypothesis that the discrete token representation of

audio data can maintain and even improve the intrinsic features essential for complex audio analysis tasks.

2. **A Codec-based CLAP Model:** We develop a comprehensive methodological framework for the application of neural audio codecs in CLAP model training. This framework serves as a guide for future research and practical implementation, outlining best practices for encoding, integrating, and fine-tuning CLAP models to leverage the full potential of neural audio codecs.
3. **Performance Benchmarks:** We establish performance benchmarks that can be utilized to evaluate the success of future endeavors in this domain. These benchmarks set a standard for comparison against emerging technologies, providing a clear measure of progress and achievement in the field.
4. **Open Source Resources:** We contribute to the open-source community by potentially sharing code used in this research. This sharing promotes collaborative progress and accessibility in the field, ensuring that the advancements made are available for broader academic and practical use ¹.

These contributions collectively aim to catalyze further research and development in the area of neural audio codecs and their application in CLAP models, ultimately driving forward the capabilities of AI systems in processing and understanding multimodal data.

1.4 Structure of the Thesis

Chapter 2: Definition and State-of-the-Art This chapter delves into the theoretical underpinnings of the research, offering a detailed review of audio representation methods, neural audio codecs, and the evolution of contrastive learning methods, particularly focusing on the CLAP model. It establishes a knowledge base that is crucial for understanding the subsequent discussions on methodology and experimentation.

¹https://github.com/dudu0liver/SMC_CodecCLAP

Chapter 3: Methodology The methodology chapter is the cornerstone of the thesis, detailing the model structures we have explored, the datasets utilized, and the evaluation strategies employed. It outlines the experimental design, providing clarity on how the research objectives have been translated into a structured experimental framework.

Chapter 4: Experiments This chapter presents the empirical backbone of the thesis, showcasing the experimental design, results, and a thorough analysis and discussion of the findings. It offers insights into the performance of various models, the impact of different audio feature extractors and embedding models, and the benefits of pre-training.

Chapter 5: Conclusions The conclusion chapter synthesizes the research findings, reflecting on the objectives outlined in the introduction and summarizing the key contributions and insights gained. It also proposes directions for future work, ensuring the research's continuity and relevance in the evolving landscape of AI research.

This structured approach ensures that each chapter builds upon the last, creating a cohesive narrative that explores the depths of neural audio codec-based CLAP models, their potential, and their implications for the future of audio processing and AI.

Chapter 2

Definition and State-of-the-Art

In order to conduct research in Sound and Music Computing (SMC), the initial step is to convert and digitally represent sound signals. This digital representation is essential for enabling computers to perform information processing, computation, modeling, simulation, and advanced AI-related tasks on the digitized data source.

In the field of audio representation learning, recent breakthroughs with Neural Audio Codecs and Contrastive Learning methods, particularly the Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining (CLAP) model, have attracted significant attention and are widely recognized in the academic community.

This chapter will begin by reviewing classical audio representation methods, then focus on discussing the Neural Audio Codecs approach and the Contrastive Learning methods represented by the CLAP model. Additionally, we will delve into the evaluation methods and applications of these methods within the SMC field, with a specific emphasis on Text-to-Audio Retrieval.

2.1 Audio Representation

In the section on audio representation, we will initially review the fundamental, classic, and mature methods of audio representation that have been widely adopted. Subsequently, we will focus on the recent significant advancements in Neural Audio

Codecs, as well as Embedding models and Latent Representation methods. These emerging techniques are reshaping the landscape of audio data processing, offering innovative approaches to understanding and utilizing audio signals within various machine learning frameworks.

Audio representation methods can be broadly categorized into several classes, each with its own set of classic techniques. Here are some of the prominent categories and their classic methods:

1. **Raw Audio Waveform:** This is the most direct form of audio representation, capturing the amplitude of sound over time. It is used as input for various deep learning models. However, it can be computationally expensive and may not reflect how sound is perceived by humans [19].
2. **Spectrogram:** A spectrogram is a visual representation of the spectrum of frequencies of a signal as it varies with time. It is generated by performing a Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) on a signal, which results in a time-frequency representation. The spectrogram provides a detailed view of the signal's spectral content over time, making it useful for observing changes in fundamental frequency and spectral envelope [20].
3. **Mel-Spectrogram:** The Mel-spectrogram is a specific type of spectrogram that has been processed through Mel filter banks. Instead of using linear frequency bins, the Mel-spectrogram uses Mel-frequency bins, which provide a non-linear representation of the audio spectrum that is more aligned with human auditory perception. This representation is often used as an intermediate step before computing Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs) [20].
 - (a) **Mel Filter Banks:** Mel filter banks emulate the human ear's sensitivity across the frequency spectrum, employing a set of band-pass filters designed according to the Mel scale—a perceptually motivated, roughly logarithmic scale of pitch. This scale provides greater resolution at lower frequencies, where human hearing is more acute, and less at higher frequencies. The computation of MFCCs initiates with the application of

these Mel filter banks to the power spectrum of the input audio signal, effectively mapping frequencies in a manner that mirrors the human auditory system's response [20].

- (b) **MFCC:** MFCCs are a compact representation of the spectral envelope of an audio signal, widely utilized in speech and audio processing. The process of computing MFCCs begins with the application of Mel Filter Banks to the power spectrum of the input speech signal. The Mel Filter Banks serve as a frequency mapping that simulates the human auditory system's response to different frequencies. After the signal is transformed into the frequency domain using the Fourier Transform (typically a Fast Fourier Transform, or FFT), the power spectrum is obtained. The Mel Filter Banks are then applied to this power spectrum to create a representation that is more perceptually aligned with human hearing. Once the power spectrum is filtered through the Mel Filter Banks, the resulting Mel-scaled spectrum is often logarithmically scaled. This step introduces a nonlinear compression that reflects the human ear's logarithmic perception of loudness. The final step in computing MFCCs involves applying a DCT to the log-scaled Mel Filter Bank energies. This transformation decorrelates the Mel Filter Bank outputs, resulting in a set of coefficients that are easier to work with for pattern recognition tasks. MFCCs typically retain only a subset of the DCT coefficients, usually the first 12-13, which capture the most important features of the speech signal. This reduces the dimensionality of the feature vector and helps in improving the performance of machine learning models. The result is a set of coefficients that capture the shape of the spectral envelope in a compact form. MFCCs are less sensitive to noise and provide a good representation for pattern recognition tasks such as speech recognition [20].

These representations each have their advantages and are chosen based on the specific requirements of the audio processing task at hand. The choice of representation can significantly impact the performance of deep learning models in audio analysis

and other audio-related applications.

2.1.1 Neural Audio Codecs

Neural audio codecs are a type of audio representation that has emerged and rapidly developed in recent years, serving the dual purpose of compression and providing a discrete tokenization suitable for machine learning tasks.

Neural audio codecs are advanced audio compression models that leverage deep learning techniques to efficiently encode and decode audio signals. They are designed to compress audio data into compact representations while preserving the quality and content of the original audio. These models have gained significant attention due to their potential to outperform traditional audio codecs by utilizing neural networks for both compression and reconstruction tasks.

The Neural Audio Codec (NAC) process involves three main components: the Encoder, Quantizer, and Decoder. The Encoder transforms the input audio signal into a latent representation, the Quantizer discretizes this representation into a set of tokens, and the Decoder reconstructs the audio signal from the quantized tokens. This process allows for efficient representation and reconstruction of audio signals, which is crucial for tasks like audio generation and processing.

1. **Encoder (E)** The Encoder function, denoted as E , maps the continuous input audio signal x into a high-dimensional latent representation z . This latent representation captures the essential features and characteristics of the audio signal, while discarding irrelevant information.

Mathematical Representation:

$$z = E(x) \tag{2.1}$$

where:

- x represents the input audio signal, which can be represented as a sequence of samples $x = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$.

- z represents the latent representation, which is typically a high-dimensional vector $z = [z_1, z_2, \dots, z_m]$.
2. **Quantizer (Q)** The Quantizer function, denoted as Q , discretizes the continuous latent representation z into a set of tokens z_q . This is achieved through vector quantization techniques, where the latent representation is compared to a set of pre-trained codebook vectors and assigned the token corresponding to the closest codebook vector.

Mathematical Representation:

$$z_q = Q(z) \tag{2.2}$$

where:

- z represents the continuous latent representation.
 - z_q represents the discrete token representation, which is a sequence of integers $z_q = [z_{q1}, z_{q2}, \dots, z_{qn}]$.
3. **Decoder (G)** The Decoder function, denoted as G , reconstructs the audio signal $\hat{x}$ from the quantized token representation z_q . This process involves reversing the quantization operation and reconstructing the continuous latent representation from the tokens, followed by converting the latent representation back into the audio signal.

Mathematical Representation:

$$\hat{x} = G(z_q) \tag{2.3}$$

where:

- z_q represents the discrete token representation.
- $\hat{x}$ represents the reconstructed audio signal, which is a sequence of samples $\hat{x} = [\hat{x}_1, \hat{x}_2, \dots, \hat{x}_n]$.

By combining these components, the Neural Audio Codec process enables efficient and high-quality representation and reconstruction of audio signals, which is crucial for tasks like audio generation and processing.

Given the simplified mathematical framework previously discussed, we can now explore a more detailed exposition of the mathematical definitions and operations that form the foundation of the Neural Audio Codec (NAC) process, taking inspiration from the UniAudio [21].

1. **Encoder (E)** The encoder is a neural network that projects the raw audio waveform $x \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times f_s}$, where d is the duration and f_s is the sampling rate, into a sequence of latent vectors z . This is typically achieved through a series of convolutional layers, possibly followed by recurrent or attention mechanisms to capture temporal dependencies. The encoder's output is a sequence of latent features that compactly represent the input audio.
2. **Quantizer (Q)** The quantizer's role is to discretize the continuous latent representation z into a set of quantized values z_q . In the context of Residual Vector Quantization (RVQ), which is a common technique in Neural Audio Compression (NAC), the quantization process is iterative. It begins with an initial quantization step that maps the latent vector h_t to the nearest codebook entry $q_{z_{1t}}$. The residual $r_t = h_t - q_{z_{1t}}$ is then quantized in subsequent steps until a desired level of accuracy is achieved. Mathematically, for each residual step k , the quantization can be expressed as:

$$z_{kt} = \arg \min_{q \in \mathcal{C}_k} \|r_t - q\|_2 \quad (2.4)$$

where $\mathcal{C}_k$ is the codebook at step k , and $\|\cdot\|_2$ denotes the L2 norm.

3. **Decoder (G)** The decoder reconstructs the audio signal from the quantized latent representation z_q . This process involves an inverse mapping from the discrete codebook indices back to a continuous latent space, followed by a series of upsampling operations to recover the original audio waveform. The

reconstruction can be represented as:

$$\hat{x} = G(z_q) = \text{Upsample}(\mathbf{Q}^T(z_q)) \quad (2.5)$$

where $\mathbf{Q}^T$ denotes the inverse mapping from the discrete codebook indices back to a continuous latent space, and Upsample represents upsampling operations that increase the temporal resolution of the signal.

4. **Residual Vector Quantization (RVQ)** RVQ is a specific instance of the quantization process that operates recursively to quantize the residuals of the previous quantization steps. Given a latent vector h_t , the RVQ process can be defined as:

$$z_{kt} = \arg \min_{q \in \mathcal{C}_k} \|h_t - \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} q_{z_{jt}}\|_2 \quad (2.6)$$

where $q_{z_{jt}}$ is the quantized vector from the j -th step, and the sum aggregates the contributions from all previous quantization steps.

5. **Training Objective** The NAC system is trained to minimize a reconstruction loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}}$, which measures the difference between the original audio x and the reconstructed audio $\hat{x}$. The overall training objective can be expressed as:

$$\mathcal{L} = \min \mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}}(x, \hat{x}) \quad (2.7)$$

This detailed mathematical framework captures the essence of the NAC process, emphasizing the iterative nature of quantization in RVQ and the multi-stage reconstruction process involving convolutional and upsampling operations in the decoder. The training objective encapsulates the pursuit of high-fidelity audio reproduction, which is central to the design of neural audio codecs.

2.1.2 Comparative Overview of Neural Audio Codecs

Based on the recent collection and understanding of the work related to Neural Audio Codecs (NACs), we have compiled a comparative [table](#). To encapsulate the essence

of various Neural Audio Codecs, we have highlighted their principal characteristics, architectural elements, and unique features.

2.1.3 Embeddings and Latent Representations

The integration of audio data with other modalities for alignment and representation enhancement often necessitates the use of audio embedding models. These models vary based on the feature extraction methods employed, with Mel-Spectrogram and neural audio codec methods being the focus of the thesis due to their current prominence and relevance in the field.

Audio embedding models are pivotal in transforming audio feature data into a condensed, semantic, and lower-dimensional format that encapsulates the audio's intrinsic characteristics. This transformation is crucial for tasks such as sound classification, contrastive learning, and synthesis. The thesis will compare the Mel-Spectrogram method with the emerging neural audio codec approach, highlighting the evolution and current state of audio embedding models within these categories.

Spectrogram-based Models: Spectrograms provide a visual representation of the audio signal's frequency spectrum over time. Models utilizing spectrograms can discern temporal and spectral features of audio. The HTS-AT[26], an innovative audio transformer model, stands out for its efficiency and effectiveness in sound classification and detection. It overcomes the limitations of memory consumption and training duration by employing a hierarchical structure and a token-semantic module. The HTS-AT processes spectrograms with reduced sequence length and computational demand through window attention and patch merging techniques, achieving state-of-the-art results on AudioSet[27] and ESC-50[28] datasets and outperforming CNN-based models in event localization tasks.

Neural Codec-Based Models: The EnCodecMAE [29] model exemplifies the use of neural audio codecs, achieving high audio compression rates without compromising perceptual quality. Inspired by BERT[30] in NLP, EnCodecMAE employs a masked autoencoder architecture adapted for the audio domain, using the

Table 1: Comparative Overview of Neural Audio Codecs (NACs)

Codec Model	Architecture	Quantization	Key Features	Bit Rate (BPS)	Sample Rate (kHz)	Applications
SoundStream [15]	Classic NAC	RVQ	Streaming SEANets as encoder and decoder, RVQ bottleneck	Not specified	24 - 48 kHz	General audio codec
Encodec [16]	Similar to SoundStream with LSTM layers and Transformer-based language model	RVQ with additional Transformer model for sequence modeling	Integration of LSTM layers and Transformer model for RVQ codes	1.5 - 24 bps	24 - 48 kHz	General audio codec
DAC [17]	Universal model with periodic activation functions and enhanced RVQ	Enhanced RVQ with factorized and L2-normalized codes	High-fidelity audio quality across diverse data types	6 - 24 bps	16 - 44.1 kHz	General audio, music, and speech
AudioDec [22]	Enhanced version of Encodec with group convolution mechanism	Group convolution and HiFi-GAN for high-fidelity audio generation	Real-time operation and high-fidelity audio generation at 48 kHz	6.4 bps	24 kHz	Real-time streaming codec
AcademiCodec [23]	Novel group-residual vector quantization technique	Group-residual vector quantization	Tailored for generation tasks with limited codebooks	2 - 3 bps	24 kHz	Generation tasks
SpeechTokenizer [24]	Unified speech tokenizer with Encoder-Decoder architecture and RVQ	RVQ with semantic and acoustic tokens	Hierarchical separation of speech information across RVQ layers	4 bps	16 kHz	Speech language models
FunCodec [25]	Frequency-domain codec with semantic information integration	RVQ with semantic tokens and residual inclusion method	Comparable performance with fewer parameters and lower computation	8 - 16 bps	16 kHz	Speech quality at low bit rates

EnCodec[16] neural audio codec to generate discrete targets for learning universal audio representations. This self-supervised learning approach enables the model to handle diverse audio tasks, including speech, music, and environmental sounds, outperforming existing models in multiple tasks and showing promise in automatic speech recognition (ASR).

2.2 Contrastive Cross-modality Pretraining

Contrastive Learning has become a pivotal approach in representation learning, particularly excelling in the domains of unsupervised learning. It is founded on the principle of deriving insightful representations by contrasting the degrees of similarity and dissimilarity among various data samples. In this section, we will undertake an examination of the fundamental framework of Contrastive Cross-modality Pretraining, encompassing prevalent computational techniques and widespread model architectures. Subsequently, we will delve into the specialized sub-domain of this field, namely, Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining.

2.2.1 CLIP Paradigm

The significant attention that contrastive learning has garnered in the realm of representation learning in recent years cannot be overlooked, with the emergence of CLIP (Contrastive Language-Image Pretraining) model [8] being a pivotal factor.

Definition and Computational Method CLIP employs a multi-modal embedding space, with separate encoders for images and text. The image encoder and text encoder are jointly trained to maximize the cosine similarity of the embeddings for the actual pairs in the batch, while minimizing the cosine similarity for incorrect pairings. The loss function used is a symmetric cross-entropy loss over these similarity scores. The model is optimized using a batch-based approach, where each batch consists of multiple (image, text) pairs.

The core computational method can be summarized as follows:

- **Feature Extraction:** The image and text are passed through their respective encoders to obtain feature representations.
- **Embedding Projection:** The feature representations are projected into a shared multi-modal embedding space.
- **Similarity Calculation:** The cosine similarity between the image and text embeddings is computed.
- **Loss Computation:** A contrastive loss is applied to update the encoders such that the similarity of correct pairs is increased, while that of incorrect pairs is decreased.

Loss Function

Particularly noteworthy is the construction and specific computation method of its loss function, which is also the loss function utilized in this thesis. It primarily comprises 3 steps.

1. Suppose a batch from the Dataloader contains N pairs of (text-image). The N texts are first encoded through a Text Encoder, which is assumed to encode each text into a one-dimensional vector of length d_t . Thus, the output of the batch's text data after being processed by the Text Encoder is $[T_1, T_2, \dots, T_N]$, with a dimension of (N, d_t) ; similarly, the N images are encoded through an Image Encoder, and if the Image Encoder encodes each image into a one-dimensional vector of length d_i , then the output of the batch's image data after being processed by the Image Encoder is $[I_1, I_2, \dots, I_N]$, with a dimension of (N, d_i) . And then these two sets of vectors will each undergo a **multimodal embedding**, the text vectors need to be multiplied by W_t to get the final text vectors. For the image vectors, there is a corresponding W_i . The role of W_t and W_i can be understood as projecting the text and image features into a multimodal feature space.

2. Among the obtained $[T_1, T_2, \dots, T_N]$ and $[I_1, I_2, \dots, I_N]$, the (text-image) pairs are corresponding, for example, T_1 corresponds to I_1 , T_2 corresponds to I_2 , and we denote these N correspondences as positive samples; the (text-image) pairs that are not originally corresponding are marked as negative samples, for example, T_1 does not correspond to I_2 , T_N does not correspond to I_{N-1} . In this way, we have N positive samples and $N^2 - N$ negative samples. These positive and negative samples can then serve as positive and negative labels to train the Text Encoder and Image Encoder.
3. We calculate the **Cosine Similarity** between I_i and T_j ($i, j \in [1, N]$), which is the vector dot product, to measure the correspondence between the respective text and image. The greater the cosine similarity, the stronger the correspondence between I_i and T_j , and vice versa. The training task then becomes very clear: by training the parameters of the Text Encoder and Image Encoder, maximize the cosine similarity of the N positive samples and minimize the cosine similarity of the $N^2 - N$ negative samples. As shown in the diagram, this means maximizing the blue values in the diagonal and minimizing the other off-diagonal values. The optimization goal can be written as:

$$\min\left(\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^N (I_i \cdot T_j) - \sum_{i=1}^N (I_i \cdot T_i)\right) \quad (2.8)$$

Based on the innovative methods mentioned above, the CLIP model has significantly advanced the application of Contrastive Learning in Representation Learning. This approach sets itself apart from conventional supervised learning techniques that necessitate labeled data to define visual concepts. It is both efficient and scalable, as illustrated by the authors' success in training CLIP on a dataset of 400 million (image, text) pairs. CLIP extends the limits by acquiring a diverse array of tasks during pre-training, encompassing OCR, geo-localization, action recognition, and various fine-grained object classifications. The zero-shot transfer performance of CLIP on more than 30 pre-existing datasets highlights its proficiency in generalizing across tasks and domains, dispensing with the requirement for task-specific training data. This marks a substantial advancement towards agile and practical zero-shot

computer vision classifiers.

2.2.2 CLAP Models

Inspired by the CLIP model, it naturally follows that if we were to replace the image data modality in the CLIP model with an audio data modality, we could potentially align language and audio, thereby obtaining an audio representation model with high generalization capabilities. This model’s zero-shot transfer performance could have many application prospects in various Music Information Retrieval (MIR) tasks.

Indeed, as anticipated, there have already been numerous attempts at building models that follow the CLIP model’s principles, including large-scale trained models, and they have demonstrated strong audio representation capabilities. Below, we will conduct a review of some of such models in this field.

The Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining (CLAP) model is an innovative approach to learning audio representations through natural language supervision[11, 12]. The model is designed to connect language and audio by employing two encoders and contrastive learning to map audio and text descriptions into a shared multimodal space. This method stands out as it does not require predefined class labels for training, thus enhancing the flexibility of the model and enabling it to predict a wide range of classes during inference.

One of the significant contributions of the CLAP model is its ability to perform zero-shot learning. Zero-shot learning allows the model to make predictions about classes that were not seen during training, thus demonstrating a high level of generalization[11].

This model marks a significant advancement in the joint learning of audio and language representations, presenting new opportunities for zero-shot inference and generalization across a variety of tasks. Particularly, after pre-training on a large-scale dataset, it enables the model to achieve SOTA results in several downstream tasks, propelling the frontiers towards the development of general-purpose audio representations.

2.2.3 Comparative Overview of CLAPs

Based on the collection and interpretation of the recent work related to CLAP models, we have compiled a comparative [table](#). To capture the essence of various CLAP models, we have emphasized their dataset scale, model architecture, generalization capabilities, and distinctive features.

Table 2: Comparative Overview of CLAPs

Model	Training Data Size	Encoder Architecture	Key Contributions & Features
CLAP [11]	128k audio-text pairs	CNN14 for audio, BERT for text	Introduction of CLAP, Evaluated on 16 tasks; Pretrained with a large collection of pairs,
CLAP 4.6M [12]	4.6M audio-text pairs	HTSAT-22 for audio, GPT2 for text	generalized to 26 downstream tasks
MuLan [13]	44 million music recordings	Resnet-50 or AST for audio, BERT for text	Versatile in music domain
LS-CLAP [14]	633,526 audio-text pairs	PANN, HTSAT for audio, CLIP transformer, BERT, RoBERTa for text	Feature fusion and keyword-to-caption augmentation
FLAP [31]	similar to LS-CLAP	audio backbone from MAViL for audio, RoBERTa for text	Masked autoencoders for efficiency
WavText5K CLAP [32]	5,000 web audio-text pairs	combination of CNN14 and HTSAT as the audio encoder, RoBERTa for text	New collection WavText5K, improved retrieval framework

2.3 Text-to-Audio Retrieval

As we are aware, the CLAP model possesses the capability to learn joint embeddings of audio and text, which empowers the model to effectively retrieve audio clips based on textual queries. This retrieval capability is a direct application of the

multimodal representations that CLAP has learned through contrastive learning. Consequently, Text-to-audio retrieval (TTA) emerges as a crucial evaluation task for the CLAP model because it mirrors real user interactions, assesses the model’s multimodal comprehension, and offers a versatile and immediate measure of the model’s effectiveness in a practical setting.

TTA is a cross-modal retrieval task that aims to retrieve a target audio clip or caption from a pool of candidates given a query in another modality, typically text[33]. This involves mapping the semantic content of the text into an audio representation space where it can be matched with audio data. This task is challenging due to the need to learn robust feature representations for both modalities and capture the fine-grained alignment between them[34, 35, 36].

2.3.1 Retrieval Metrics

In text-to-audio retrieval, the most widely used evaluation metrics are Mean Average Precision (MAP) and Recall.

Mean Average Precision (mAP) is extensively used because it provides a single-figure measure of quality across recall levels. This is particularly important in text-to-audio retrieval tasks where the position of relevant audio clips within the retrieved list matters. mAP considers both precision and recall, making it sensitive to the ranking of relevant items. This sensitivity is crucial in applications where users are more likely to engage with top-ranked results[37].

- **Precision Sensitivity:** mAP evaluates the precision at each rank position where a relevant item is retrieved, averaging these precision values. This ensures that models are rewarded for retrieving relevant items earlier in the result list.
- **Holistic Measure:** By averaging the precision over all relevant items, mAP provides a comprehensive assessment of the retrieval model’s performance.

Definition: Mean Average Precision at i (mAP@ i) is a metric that measures the

average precision of the top i retrieved items across all queries. It reflects both the precision and the position of relevant items within the top i results[38].

Formula:

$$\text{mAP}@i = \frac{1}{|Q|} \sum_{q \in Q} \text{AP}@i(q) \quad (2.9)$$

where

$$\text{AP}@i(q) = \frac{1}{\min(i, R_q)} \sum_{k=1}^i P(k) \cdot \text{rel}(k) \quad (2.10)$$

- $|Q|$ is the number of queries.
- R_q is the number of relevant documents for query q .
- $P(k)$ is the precision at rank k .
- $\text{rel}(k)$ is an indicator function that is 1 if the item at rank k is relevant, and 0 otherwise.

Recall at i ($\mathbf{R}@i$) is favored in text-to-audio retrieval for its ability to measure the proportion of queries for which at least one relevant audio clip is retrieved within the top i results. This metric is particularly useful in evaluating the effectiveness of retrieval systems in ensuring that relevant items are not missed[37].

- **User-Centric Evaluation:** $\mathbf{R}@i$ directly reflects the user’s experience by indicating the likelihood that a user will find at least one relevant audio clip in the top i results, which is critical for practical usability.
- **Binary Relevance:** $\mathbf{R}@i$ simplifies evaluation to a binary measure (relevant or not), making it straightforward to interpret and compare across different models and datasets.

Definition: Recall at i ($\mathbf{R}@i$) is a metric that measures the proportion of queries for which at least one of the top i retrieved items is relevant. It indicates the ability of the system to retrieve at least one relevant item within the top i positions[38].

Formula:

$$R@i = \frac{1}{|Q|} \sum_{q \in Q} \left[\max_{k \in \{1, \dots, i\}} \text{rel}(k) \right] \quad (2.11)$$

- $|Q|$ is the number of queries.
- $\text{rel}(k)$ is an indicator function that is 1 if the item at rank k is relevant for query q , and 0 otherwise.

The combination of mAP and R@i provides a comprehensive framework for evaluating text-to-audio retrieval systems. mAP captures the precision of relevant items across their ranks, while R@i ensures that relevant items are present within the top results. Together, these metrics offer a balanced view of both the accuracy and recall capabilities of retrieval models.

Chapter 3

Methodology

In this chapter, we focus on the discussion of the methodology pertinent to the thesis. The methodology encompasses a detailed discourse on the model’s architecture, the dataset utilized, and the evaluative approaches following the training of the models.

3.1 Model Structure

In the State-of-the-Art section, we have already gained an understanding of a typical CLAP model, which is composed of two major modules: one for text encoding and the other for audio encoding. The objective of our thesis is to experiment with replacing the traditional audio encoder module in the CLAP model with a novel audio encoder, NAC, to observe its performance and explore methods that could enhance the utilization of NAC within the CLAP model. Thus, the methodology of the thesis is primarily centered around the audio encoder module, with the main goal of designing a set of more comprehensive and fair experiments to evaluate the performance achievable by NAC as an audio encoder module within the CLAP model. It is particularly noted that the representation models for the output of NAC as input are just beginning to be explored in the scientific community and are still very immature. Determining the applicability of NAC as an audio representation method in the CLAP model based solely on the performance of a few existing representation models would be premature.

Therefore, in the CLAP model adopted for the thesis, we have designed two distinct configurations for the audio encoder module. In one model structure, similar to the classic CLAP model, where the audio encoder module consists of an audio feature extractor and an audio embedding model. In the other model structure, we have simplified the audio encoder module by removing the audio embedding model, allowing the results generated by the audio feature extractor to serve as the final audio representation in the subsequent alignment calculations of the CLAP model. We believe this approach will facilitate a more equitable assessment and reveal the potential capabilities of the tokens or codes produced by NAC as an audio representation. The specific model structures are illustrated in Figures 1 and 2.

3.1.1 CLAP Structure I

Figure 1: CLAP Structure I

Figure 1 depicts a classic CLAP model structure, which is composed of two main components: the text encoder module and the audio encoder module. Within the text encoder module, there are two subcomponents: the text tokenizer and the text embedding model. The text tokenizer is responsible for mapping text into tokens. The text embedding model processes the text tokens into higher-level semantic fea-

tures and maps them into the latent space. The audio encoder module is similar to the text encoder module, consisting of a tokenizer and an embedding model for information processing. The raw audio first enters the audio feature extractor to be vectorized and to extract audio features. Subsequently, the feature data is sent to the audio embedding model to extract higher-level abstract audio features and map them into the latent space. During the training phase of the model, text-audio pairs will enter the respective text and audio encoder modules based on their data modalities. After feature extraction for each modality, the feature data is then sent to the corresponding MLP (Multi-Layer Perceptron) network layer. The MLP maps the features to the same dimension and then constructs a similarity matrix. After calculating the similarity, the loss is computed through a contrastive learning loss function.

It is worth noting that in the model training of this thesis, for models based on **CLAP Structure I**, the tokenizers in the dual encoders are kept frozen during training, while the rest of the model is trained.

3.1.2 CLAP Structure II

Figure 2: CLAP Structure II

Figure 2 presents a CLAP model structure similar to that of Figure 1, with the

exception of a simplification in the audio encoder modules. We have eliminated the audio embedding model, retaining only the audio feature extractor. Consequently, after the audio modality data undergoes feature extraction through the audio feature extractor, it will proceed directly to its corresponding MLP (Multi-Layer Perceptron) network layer, where it will subsequently engage in contrastive learning computations.

During the training of models based on **CLAP Structure II**, we continue to maintain the tokenizers within the dual encoders in a frozen state, while training the remaining components.

3.2 Dataset

For all model training and evaluation, we have adopted the Clotho[39] dataset as a unified resource. This approach ensures that all models are subjected to fair experimentation and comparison under the same dataset conditions.

The Clotho dataset comprises 4981 audio samples, each lasting between 15 to 30 seconds, and 24,905 captions with lengths ranging from 8 to 20 words. The audio samples are sourced from the Freesound¹ platform, and the captions are crowd-sourced using Amazon Mechanical Turk² with annotators from English-speaking countries. Clotho emphasizes diversity in audio content and captions and ensures that the splits of the data do not impede the training or evaluation of methods. Post-processing removes unique words, named entities, and speech transcriptions.

It is noteworthy that the number of captions in the dataset is five times the number of audio samples. The reason for that is due to the intentional design of the dataset to promote diversity in the descriptions of the audio content. Each audio sample in the dataset is accompanied by five different captions, which are collected to capture a variety of perceptual interpretations of the audio signal. This approach allows the dataset to better represent the subjective nature of audio captioning, where different listeners might perceive and describe the same audio signal in distinct ways.

¹<https://freesound.org/>

²<https://www.mturk.com/>

In the specific training and evaluation phases of this experimental project, since we are utilizing the CLAP model as the foundational model architecture, our data preparation is conducted in pairs of text and audio. Therefore, when calculating the specific number of text-audio pairs, we should note that due to the quantity of text pairs being five times that of the audio pairs, the actual number of text-audio pairs in training and evaluation aligns with the number of text pairs.

The following Table 3 outlines the specific distribution of the dataset:

Table 3: Clotho dataset distribution

Split Type	Number of Audio Samples	Number of Captions	Number of Text-Audio Pairs
Development	2893	14465	14465
Evaluation	1045	5225	5225
Testing	1043	5215	5215

3.3 Evaluation

During the model evaluation phase, for the two sets of models trained under the **CLAP Structure I** and **CLAP Structure II** model architectures, we uniformly adopt Text-to-Audio Retrieval and Audio-to-Caption Retrieval as the evaluation tasks. For the specific definition of the Information Retrieval task, please refer to section 2.3. The reason for adopting this bidirectional evaluation approach is based on the following considerations:

- **Comprehensive Evaluation:** By employing two distinct retrieval tasks, you can assess the model’s performance from different angles. The Text to Audio retrieval evaluates how well the model can match text descriptions to audio clips, while the Audio to Captions retrieval assesses the model’s ability to generate accurate text descriptions for given audio clips.
- **Cross-Modality Understanding:** Utilizing both retrieval tasks ensures that the model is evaluated in both directions (text-to-audio and audio-to-text),

providing a more balanced and thorough evaluation. This bidirectional assessment helps in identifying strengths and weaknesses in the model’s understanding and generation capabilities.

- **Robustness:** By testing the model with both tasks, researchers can ensure that the model is not overfitting to one specific type of retrieval task. It promotes the development of models that are robust and perform well across different types of input and output pairs.
- **Real-World Applicability:** For practical purposes, such as the future possibility of deploying the high-performing CLAP model as a backend search engine for the Freesound³ platform. These evaluation tasks simulate real-world scenarios where users might search for audio content using text queries (e.g., searching for sound effects using descriptions) or need textual information based on audio inputs (e.g., transcribing spoken or semantic content). Therefore, such evaluations ensure that the models are practically useful and relevant.

By evaluating CLAP models with these dual retrieval tasks, we can derive more nuanced insights into model performance.

In addition, the specific evaluation metrics we employ are: mAP@10, R@1, R@5, R@10, and R@50. The detailed definitions, equations, and advantages of employing them for Text-to-Audio (TTA) tasks have been elucidated in section 2.3. Here, only a brief explanation is provided for reference.

- **mAP@10 (Mean Average Precision at 10):** Captures both the precision and ranking of relevant items within the top 10 results, offering a balanced view of the retrieval accuracy and relevance.
- **R@1, R@5, R@10, R@50 (Recall at 1, 5, 10, 50):** These metrics measure percentage of total relevant items that are retrieved within the top 1, 5, 10, or

³<https://freesound.org/>

50 results on average for all queries, respectively, thus highlighting the system's ability to recall relevant items across different cutoff points.

Considering the characteristics of the dataset, where the number of texts is five times that of the audios, the metrics might exhibit some noteworthy characteristics:

- **Text-to-Audio Retrieval:** Performance might be more challenging to optimize due to the complexity of matching textual descriptions with diverse audio content.
- **Audio-to-Captions Retrieval:** Since each audio clip can be associated with multiple captions, this task might show higher recall values at higher cutoffs (e.g., R@50) compared to text-to-audio retrieval.

Whether the final experimental results support the hypotheses we have made here, let us proceed to the experimental section to find out.

Chapter 4

Experiments

This chapter delineates the experimental framework of the thesis, including the design, results, and a comprehensive analysis and discussion of the findings. It delves into the intricacies of the models trained, the hyperparameters employed, and the metrics assessed within a text-to-audio retrieval paradigm. The analysis gauges the performance benchmarks against initial expectations, evaluating the results' contribution to the thesis' objectives and providing valuable insights for future research endeavors.

4.1 Experimental Design

The study encompasses seven models, bifurcated into two structural categories: CLAP Structure I and CLAP Structure II. These models are distinguished by their audio data representation methodologies, namely Mel Filter Banks and NAC, and the specific audio representation models: Mel, DAC, and EnCodec. The subsequent sections elucidate the groupings, configurations, hyperparameters, and subtleties of each model's training regimen.

Common Configurations:

- Audio clips are uniformly truncated to a duration of 10 seconds.

- A pre-trained Bert-Base-Uncased underpins the text encoder for all models, with a token limit of 30, unfrozen during training.
- A Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) functions as the projector layer, compressing the final embed size to 1024, also unfrozen during training.
- A consistent batch size of 32 is utilized across all models.
- The training epoch count is standardized to 15.
- Optimizer settings are uniform, featuring a learning rate of 5e-5, Adam optimizer with betas of [0.9, 0.999], epsilon of 1e-8, and a momentum of 0.9, with a 2-epoch warmup.

The models' variations are primarily in the audio encoder module, which is expounded through the introduction of the audio feature extractor and audio embedding model for each. For brevity and clarity, models will be referenced by simplified labels in subsequent discussions.

Experimental Design Table

The table below encapsulates the experimental design for the seven models, highlighting their structural and parametric differences, and detailing their unique audio feature extraction and embedding strategies.

Table 4: Model Configurations

Model Abbreviation	CLAP Model Structure	NAC	Audio Feature Extractor	Extractor Configuration	Audio Embedding Model
Mel	II	NO	Log Mel-filterbank	Standard configuration	None
Mel_ HTSAT	I	NO	Log Mel-filterbank	Standard configuration Codebooks:	HTSAT
DAC	II	YES	DAC	4, Sample Rate: 16,000 Codebooks:	None
DAC_ HTSAT	I	YES	DAC	8, Sample Rate: 16,000	HTSAT
DAC_ HTSAT_ PreT	I	YES	DAC	Same as DAC_ HTSAT	HTSAT (pre-trained)
EnCodec	II	YES	EnCodec	Sample Rate: 44,100 Codebooks:	None
EnCodec- MAE	I	YES	EnCodec	8, Sample Rate: 24,000	EnCodec- MAE (pre-trained)

In the table, only the models labeled as 'pre-trained' in the 'Audio Embedding Model' column have utilized pre-trained weights for their audio embedding models. Given that each audio embedding model has a distinct architecture, achieving uniformity is challenging. However, post-MLP projection, the output dimensions of the audio encoder module in the similarity matrix are standardized, with a consistent dimension of 1024.

4.2 Experimental Results

The results for the models evaluated on text-to-audio (t2a) and audio-to-text (a2t) retrieval metrics are presented in the tables below:

Text-to-Audio Retrieval Metrics

Table 5: Text-to-Audio Retrieval Metrics

Models/t2a Metrics	mAP@10	R@1	R@5	R@10	R@50
Mel	2.553	1.091	4.383	7.502	25.646
DAC	3.213	1.339	5.435	9.454	29.722
Encodec	4.359	1.895	7.311	12.938	36.249
Mel_HTSAT	8.249	3.694	13.818	22.737	53.703
DAC_HTSAT	4.966	2.048	8.593	13.665	39.081
DAC_HTSAT_PreT	8.046	3.675	13.761	21.761	52.115
EnCodecMAE	13.622	6.832	22.411	33.359	66.488

Audio-to-Text Retrieval Metrics

Table 6: Audio-to-Text Retrieval Metrics

Models/a2t Metrics	mAP@10	R@1	R@5	R@10	R@50
Mel	0.635	0.861	3.827	7.081	24.211
DAC	0.871	1.339	5.072	9.282	28.995
Encodec	1.062	1.914	6.411	12.632	38.086
Mel_HTSAT	2.421	3.062	13.014	22.679	53.014
DAC_HTSAT	1.269	1.435	7.656	13.971	37.799
DAC_HTSAT_PreT	2.484	3.541	14.067	21.435	52.153
EnCodecMAE	4.708	6.603	22.775	33.301	69.473

Comparison Chart

To gain a more intuitive understanding of data trends and the comparative relationships between metrics, we have consolidated the scores from two tasks into a single composite score. This new metric is designed to reflect the average performance of each metric across the two tasks. Following this consolidation, we have created the chart as illustrated below:

Figure 3: The chart illustrates the combined metrics for the text-to-audio and audio-to-text retrieval tasks. The values depicted represent the average performance of each model across both tasks, encompassing all the evaluation metrics. Counting from left to right, the first three models are based on the CLAP Structure II, while the subsequent ones are built on the CLAP Structure I, with an enhanced audio encoder module that incorporates an audio embedding model.

4.3 Analysis and Discussion

Impact of Model Structure

To gain clearer insights from the result data, we have categorized the outcomes into a four-quadrant diagram based on the different CLAP structures the models belong to and the distinct retrieval tasks they perform.

Figure 4: The charts provide a visual comparison of the performance metrics for the different models categorized under CLAP Structure I and CLAP Structure II for both text-to-audio (t2a) and audio-to-text (a2t) retrieval tasks.

CLAP Structure I vs. CLAP Structure II: The performance comparison between these two structures reveals significant differences. Refer to Figure 4, CLAP Structure I models, such as Mel_HTSAT and DAC_HTSAT, generally outperform their CLAP Structure II counterparts. This suggests that the incorporation of an audio embedding model in the audio encoder module considerably enhances model performance. The presence of advanced embedding techniques in CLAP Structure I likely allows for more nuanced and informative audio representations, which are crucial for improving retrieval accuracy.

Comparison of Audio Feature Extractors

Log Mel-filterbank vs. DAC vs. EnCodec: Upon analyzing the performance of models that utilize CLAP Structure II, as shown in the CLAP Structure II charts of Figure 4, it is observed that both DAC and EnCodec-based models exhibit better performance than those relying on Log Mel-filterbank features. This indicates that neural network-based audio encoding methods, such as DAC and EnCodec, capture richer and more discriminative audio features, leading to improved retrieval performance. The superiority of these methods underscores the importance of advanced feature extraction techniques in handling complex audio data.

Comparison of Audio Embedding Models

Mel_HTSAT vs. DAC_HTSAT: Despite both models leveraging the HTSAT audio embedding model, DAC_HTSAT does not outperform Mel_HTSAT, as illustrated in the CLAP Structure I charts of Figure 4. This result may be ascribed to the HTSAT model’s design, which is tailored for Log Mel-filterbank features rather than DAC. Furthermore, the diminished input feature size of DAC (32,000 as opposed to the higher dimensional input of Mel, which is 64,064) could restrict the model’s capacity to fully harness the capabilities of HTSAT.

Mel_HTSAT vs. DAC_HTSAT_PreT: When examining the comparison between these two models as depicted in the CLAP Structure I charts of Figure 4, it is evident that both utilize the HTSAT audio embedding model type. However, the model DAC_HTSAT_PreT incorporates pre-trained weights, and we observe that pre-training substantially enhances performance. This highlights the value of transfer learning, where leveraging pre-trained weights allows the model to utilize prior knowledge and capture more effective feature representations, leading to enhanced performance.

HTSAT and EnCodecMAE: Introducing HTSAT and EnCodecMAE as audio embedding models results in marked performance improvements. EnCodecMAE, in particular, demonstrates a significant improvement in the Structure I models, as

shown in the CLAP Structure I charts of Figure 4. This indicates that advanced audio embedding models are highly effective at converting audio features into beneficial representations for retrieval tasks. This finding supports the potential of combining advanced embedding models with pre-training techniques to achieve superior results.

Mel_HTSAT vs. EnCodecMAE: The pre-trained EnCodecMAE model significantly outperforms others across various performance metrics, as illustrated in Figure 4. Despite using discrete audio codes generated by EnCodec for tokenizing audio features, the EnCodecMAE model demonstrates exceptional retrieval performance. This indicates that designing specialized audio embedding models for NAC generated codes, coupled with pre-training methods, is a promising approach for enhancing the audio representation capability in CLAP models. The success of EnCodecMAE suggests that NAC methods hold significant promise for future advancements in CLAP model development.

Comparison of Metric Performance

mAP@10 and R@1, R@5, R@10, R@50: mAP@10, a comprehensive metric accounting for the top 10 retrieval results, often correlates highly with R@10 and R@50 metrics. This trend suggests that as the retrieval range expands, the mAP@K and R@K metrics converge, reflecting consistent retrieval performance across different cutoffs.

a2t vs. t2a: Metrics such as mAP@10 and R@1 reveal that audio-to-text (a2t) retrieval is generally more challenging than text-to-audio (t2a) retrieval. This discrepancy is likely due to the high dimensionality and complexity of audio data, making it more difficult to accurately retrieve text from audio representations. Despite initial expectations, where audio-to-captions retrieval might show higher recall values due to the greater number of texts, the balanced loss method in dual encoders like the CLAP model ensures equilibrium in performance across tasks.

Key Insights

The experimental results and subsequent analysis lead to several key insights:

Model Structure: CLAP Structure I, with its enhanced audio embedding model, significantly outperforms CLAP Structure II, suggesting that incorporating an audio embedding model is crucial for achieving higher performance in text-to-audio and audio-to-text retrieval tasks.

Audio Feature Extractors: Advanced audio encoding methods like DAC and EnCodec outperform traditional Log Mel-filterbank features, indicating that neural audio codec based feature extractors provide richer and more discriminative audio representations.

Pre-training: Models that leverage pre-trained weights, such as DAC_HTSAT_PreT and EnCodecMAE, exhibit superior performance, underscoring the benefits of transfer learning and pre-trained models in capturing more effective feature representations.

Composite Metric: The composite metric introduced in the analysis provides a holistic view of model performance, facilitating easier comparison across different models and configurations.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

The exploration of neural audio codecs within the Contrastive Language-Audio Pre-training (CLAP) framework has yielded profound insights and promising results, significantly contributing to the field of audio representation learning. This chapter synthesizes the research findings, reflecting on the objectives outlined in the Introduction and summarizing the key contributions and insights gained. It also proposes directions for future work, ensuring the research's continuity and relevance in the evolving landscape of AI research.

5.1 Summary of Findings

The experimental results, particularly those of the EnCodecMAE model, have validated the feasibility of employing discrete tokens as a representation of audio modality within the CLAP structure. The such models have demonstrated superior performance compared to those based on traditional Mel-Spectrogram representations, highlighting the potential of neural audio codec-based CLAP in advancing the state-of-the-art in audio representation and processing.

5.1.1 Key Insights from the Integration of Neural Audio Codecs

Our exploration has provided valuable insights into the optimal integration of neural audio codec-based audio encoder modules into CLAP models:

Benefits of Pre-training: Pre-training the embedding model prior to its integration into the CLAP model, followed by fine-tuning through contrastive learning, effectively boosts the model’s capabilities. This approach allows the embedding model to converge more readily, leveraging pre-trained weights to capture more effective feature representations.

5.2 Contributions

The exploration of neural audio codecs within the CLAP framework has yielded a rich tapestry of contributions that resonate with the initial Expected Contributions set forth in the Introduction. These contributions not only validate the theoretical underpinnings of our research but also chart a course for future advancements in the field of audio representation learning.

1. **Innovative Integration of Neural Audio Codecs:** Our research introduces an innovative approach to integrating neural audio codecs into CLAP models, offering a fresh perspective on audio representation in cross-modal AI systems. This integration is more than a mere technical feat; it represents a significant leap in how audio data can be encoded and understood within AI models, aligning with the motivation to explore the potential of advanced audio representation techniques.
2. **Empirical Validation of Model Effectiveness:** Through rigorous experimentation, we have provided empirical evidence that supports the effectiveness of neural audio codecs in enhancing the representational power of CLAP models. The results, particularly from the EnCodecMAE model, validate our hypothesis that discrete token representation can preserve and even enhance the intrinsic features necessary for sophisticated audio representing tasks, echoing the objective to conduct a feasibility study.
3. **Development of Methodological Framework:** We have developed a comprehensive methodological framework for the application of neural audio codecs in CLAP model training. This framework, which includes best practices for

encoding, integrating, and fine-tuning the model, serves as a guide for future research and practical implementation, fulfilling our objective to explore methodological strategies.

4. **Establishment of Performance Benchmarks:** Our research has significantly contributed to the field by establishing robust performance benchmarks within the specific domain of Text-to-Audio Retrieval (TTA). These benchmarks are crucial for evaluating the effectiveness of CLAP models that incorporate neural audio codecs and provide a standardized measure against which future models can be compared.
5. **Provision of Open Source Resources:** By potentially sharing code used in this research, we contribute to the open-source community, promoting collaborative progress and accessibility in the field. This sharing of resources is a testament to our commitment to fostering a community that builds upon and expands the work initiated in this thesis ¹.

These contributions collectively represent a significant step forward in the application of neural audio codecs for audio representation in AI models. They encapsulate the essence of our research and set a foundation for further exploration and development in this exciting and rapidly evolving domain.

5.3 Further Work

The journey of integrating neural audio codecs into CLAP models is one of continuous exploration and refinement. Building upon the findings and contributions of this research, several promising avenues for future work have emerged, each with the potential to further the boundaries of audio representation learning and its applications.

1. **Development of Universal Audio Embedding Models:** A pivotal area for future research is the development of a universal audio embedding model

¹https://github.com/dudu0liver/SMC_CodecCLAP

tailored for NAC codes. This model should adeptly capture the nuances of the discrete tokens produced by neural audio codecs, providing a robust foundation for various audio processing tasks.

2. **Large-Scale Dataset Training:** To fully harness the capabilities of advanced audio embedding models, it will be essential to train them on large-scale, diverse datasets. This will enable the models to learn rich and generalized representations, applicable across a wide array of audio phenomena.
3. **Optimization of Pre-training Strategies:** The pre-training phase is critical in establishing a solid foundation for the embedding models. Future work should focus on optimizing pre-training strategies to ensure that the models can effectively leverage prior knowledge and adapt to the specific characteristics of neural audio codec outputs.
4. **Enhanced Fine-tuning Techniques:** Once the embedding models are integrated into the CLAP framework, fine-tuning techniques will need to be refined. This will ensure that the models can seamlessly align with the contrastive learning objectives of the CLAP model, enhancing overall performance in multimodal tasks.
5. **Expansion to Downstream Tasks:** To thoroughly evaluate the generalizability of CLAP models with neural audio codecs, it will be important to expand the range of downstream tasks. This will provide a comprehensive assessment of the models' capabilities and their robustness across different applications.
6. **Innovation in Design and Training Methodologies:** The design and training of neural audio codec-based CLAP models present a fertile ground for innovation. Future research should explore novel methodologies that can further enhance the effectiveness of these models in handling complex audio-related tasks.
7. **Cross-Disciplinary Applications:** The potential applications of neural audio codec-based CLAP models extend beyond the scope of this research. Fu-

ture work should investigate how these models can be applied in interdisciplinary contexts, such as in conjunction with other modalities or within different domains of AI.

8. **Benchmarking and Evaluation Methodologies:** As the field progresses, it will be crucial to develop and refine benchmarking and evaluation methodologies. These will need to keep pace with the evolving capabilities of CLAP models, ensuring that performance assessments remain relevant and insightful.

By pursuing these avenues of research, we can ensure that the integration of neural audio codecs into CLAP models continues to evolve, driven by a commitment to innovation and a desire to unlock new potentials in audio representation and retrieval. The future of this field holds great promise, and it is through this ongoing work that we will realize the full transformative potential of neural audio codec-based CLAP in AI.

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Appendix A

Experiments Logging

In this thesis, comprehensive logging of the project was conducted using the Weights & Biases (WandB) tool. Below are the trajectories of loss reduction for various models, facilitating an understanding of the convergence status of each model.

Figure 5: Loss of each models.